

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type2_c_Topo		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:35:52 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	18.57	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.2833	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type2_c_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:35:52 PM		
Studiabale type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.444	μm	
Min:	-2.51	μm	
Max:	1.933	μm	
Size:	156831	digits	
Spacing:	0.02833	nm	
NM-points ratio:	11.11 % (1000083 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:35:52 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.444	μm	
Size:	156831	digits	
Spacing:	0.02833	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.7134	μm	
Ssk	-0.5911		
Sku	3.178		
Sp	1.922	μm	
Sv	2.522	μm	
Sz	4.444	μm	
Sa	0.5679	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	6.446	%	
Smc	0.8053	μm	
Sxp	1.715	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	20.13	μm	
Str	*****		
Std	24.76	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1632		
Sdr	1.269	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.02476	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.8301	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.02476	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.6769	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.7285	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.1016	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

- ISO 25178 8.
- Furrow 9.
- Texture direction 10.
- Texture isotropy 11.
- SSFA 12.

Warnings

Str: The autocorrelation lobe touches the edges. Try to level the...

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	2.758	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.6647	µm
Mean density of furrows	3549	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	26.48	°
Second direction	44.99	°
Third direction	0.004697	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	40.63	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

